

Advancing materials discovery through artificial intelligence

Martin Otyepka^{a,b}, Martin Pykal^a, Michal Otyepka^{a,c,*}

^a Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, The Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute (CATRIN), Palacký University Olomouc, Šlechtitěla 27, 77900 Olomouc, Czech Republic

^b Center of Advanced Technologies and Engineering (CATEN), Technická 375/3, 708 00 Ostrava-Pustkovec, Czech Republic

^c IT4Innovations, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming materials science by accelerating the design, synthesis, and characterization of novel materials. This review highlights how AI, including machine learning, deep learning, and generative models, is reshaping the discovery pipeline. AI-driven approaches enable rapid property prediction, inverse design, and simulation of complex systems such as nanomaterials and solid-state materials, often matching the accuracy of *ab initio* methods at a fraction of the computational cost. Machine-learning-based force fields provide efficient and transferable models for large-scale simulations, while explainable AI improves transparency and physical interpretability. In synthesis, AI supports synthesis planning, reaction optimization, and the development of autonomous laboratories capable of real-time feedback and adaptive experimentation. Tools originally developed for organic molecules are increasingly adapted for complex materials, including those with structural, thermodynamic, or kinetic constraints. AI also advances in situ characterization, automating tasks such as spectral interpretation and defect identification. Despite rapid progress, challenges remain in model generalizability, standardized data formats, experimental validation, and energy efficiency. The review underscores the importance of hybrid approaches combining physical knowledge with data-driven models and calls for open-access datasets also including negative experiments and ethical frameworks to ensure responsible deployment. Future directions include modular AI systems, improved human-AI collaboration, integration with techno-economic analysis, and field-deployable robotics. By aligning computational innovation with practical implementation, AI is poised to drive scalable, sustainable, and interpretable materials discovery, turning autonomous experimentation into a powerful engine for scientific advancement.

1. Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into materials science is reshaping the way new materials are designed, synthesized, and characterized, offering a paradigm shift toward more efficient, targeted, and sustainable research and development. Over the past decade, AI has increasingly permeated all domains of science, establishing itself not only as a tool for automation but as a cognitive partner capable of enhancing decision-making, accelerating discovery, and uncovering novel scientific insights. This transformative potential is especially relevant to materials research, where the complexity of chemical and structural space often poses significant challenges to traditional trial-and-error methodologies.

AI can be broadly defined as a computational technology enabling machines to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence

such as pattern recognition, decision-making, and language processing. Its efficacy in scientific domains stems largely from machine learning (ML) and, in particular, deep learning (DL), i.e., two nested subfields within AI. ML refers to algorithms that learn from data without being explicitly programmed for specific tasks, while DL utilizes multi-layered artificial neural networks (NN) to extract increasingly abstract features from raw input data, often surpassing human-level performance in complex tasks such as image recognition or language translation [1,2]. In practice, the successful deployment of ML and DL models in materials research typically follows a systematic workflow. This involves the creation and curation of high-quality databases, the design and training of predictive models, rigorous validation to ensure accuracy, and iterative cycles of usage and re-training. Fig. 1 summarizes this general workflow, which provides the foundation for more advanced AI applications discussed in the following sections.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Michal.otyepka@upol.cz (M. Otyepka).

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Among the most prominent AI technologies today is generative AI, which not only processes and analyzes data but also generates new content, including text, images, audio, and also molecular structures. While generative AI models such as generative adversarial networks (GANs) and Transformers have shown promising advanced in fields like drug discovery, identification of small molecules from mass spectra [3], and organic synthesis, their application within materials science remains still in its early stages. Sparse and heterogeneous datasets, the complexity inherent to modeling solid-state systems, and significant challenges in validating computational predictions against experimental data have restricted their adoption. Moreover, the intricate complexity of nanomaterials, much like those of biomolecules, often involves systems comprising thousands of atoms, including surrounding solvent molecules, which together push the boundaries of current computational capabilities and making large-scale simulations using ML interatomic potentials (MLIPs) a persistent challenge. Nevertheless, ongoing improvements in data infrastructure, computational efficiency, and modeling approaches indicate substantial potential for broader integration of generative techniques in future materials science research. Any case, for the simulation of physical properties and structure optimization, MLIPs and DL NNs are increasingly employed [4–6].

Despite the impressive accuracy of advanced AI models, particularly deep NNs, their black box nature often presents a significant barrier to scientific adoption, especially in materials science where physical interpretability is essential for deriving mechanistic insights. This challenge has driven growing interest in explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), a branch of ML that aims to improve model transparency and interpretability without sacrificing predictive performance [7]. XAI techniques such as feature attribution maps, surrogate models, and concept-based visualization enable researchers to dissect model behavior, reveal the physical relevance of input features, and elucidate underlying structure–property relationships, as demonstrated for example in studies of atomic-scale magnetic materials [8] and catalysts [9]. These methods support the validation of ML predictions against known physical laws, facilitate hypothesis generation, and guide experimental design by highlighting causal or correlative drivers of materials behavior.

In parallel with interpretability, uncertainty quantification (UQ) is increasingly recognized as a cornerstone for the scientific adoption of AI

models in materials research [10], particularly in safety-critical or resource-intensive applications. Bayesian frameworks and kernel-based methods naturally provide confidence intervals and error estimates [11, 12], while ensemble strategies and active learning enable detection of out-of-distribution inputs and guide acquisition of informative new data (see [13]). Importantly, UQ not only improves robustness and reproducibility but also enhances trust by allowing researchers to calibrate predictions against experimental error bars. Coupling UQ with XAI therefore establishes a dual framework in which models are not only accurate but also transparent and reliable. Together, these approaches help to close the gap between statistical performance and scientific understanding, reinforcing responsible deployment of AI in materials discovery [14].

In materials research, AI has shown its value across the entire material development pipeline, i.e., from inverse design and property prediction to synthetic route planning and experimental automation (Fig. 2). For instance, ML models can identify correlations between composition, structure, and material properties using large datasets derived from high-throughput computations, databases (e.g., Materials Project, Open Catalyst Project), and literature mining [15–17]. A breakthrough is the ability to implement inverse design workflows, where the desired properties are specified as inputs, and the model proposes candidate materials often accelerating the discovery process by orders of magnitude [18].

AI is also transforming the planning and execution of chemical synthesis. In organic chemistry, platforms such as IBM RXN for Chemistry, which is trained on chemical reactions derived from publicly available patents, can predict viable synthetic pathways for organic compounds [19]. Similarly, DL retrosynthesis tools such as AiZynthFinder and Molecular Transformer have demonstrated success in designing multi-step synthesis procedures with high accuracy [20]. While these tools are primarily tailored for molecular synthesis, analogous developments are emerging in the context of materials synthesis. AI-driven workflows are increasingly being integrated into robotic platforms capable of autonomously planning, executing, and optimizing experimental procedures. These autonomous laboratories operate in closed-loop fashion, adjusting synthesis parameters in real time based on AI-generated hypotheses and experimental feedback [21,22], thus marking a significant step toward self-driving laboratories for materials

Fig. 1. General workflow for developing and deploying machine learning models in materials research, from database creation and model design to validation, usage, and iterative re-training.

Fig. 2. Overview of the AI-driven nanomaterials design workflow, linking materials data infrastructure, AI/ML tools, and resulting applications.

discovery and optimization.

Furthermore, AI models can be integrated into characterization pipelines, facilitating real-time data analysis, noise filtering, spectral interpretation, and even structure determination from microscopy or diffraction data [23–25]. These capabilities not only improve efficiency but also reduce human error and open the door to real-time feedback and control in experimental systems. This field has a great potential to be penetrated by AI based systems, which can provide robust material characterization free of human bias. One can expect that a new standard for material characterization may emerge due to wide utilization of AI-based tools in this domain.

Beyond technical applications, AI, particularly large language models (LLMs), has found increasing use in supporting auxiliary research activities, including language editing, data visualization, project management, and even automated hypothesis generation [26]. Distinct from such auxiliary roles, this review centers on the transformative applications of AI in materials design, synthesis, and characterization, providing an integrated account of current capabilities, representative case studies, and open challenges. Compared with prior reviews (e.g., [27,28] and numerous others cited throughout this article), our contribution lies in drawing explicit connections between recent conceptual advances in AI (LLMs, agents, XAI) and their integration with experimental realization, computational modeling, and data infrastructures, particularly within the context of autonomous laboratories and FAIR principles. We additionally underscore emerging but underexplored topics, including computational sustainability, the systematic inclusion of negative data, and ethical governance frameworks. Accordingly, this review is tailored to materials chemists and engineers seeking actionable guidance for incorporating AI into their workflows, as well as computational and data scientists interested in translating algorithmic advances into real-world materials discovery. We hope that this text will inspire researchers across materials chemistry and related disciplines to actively integrate discussed AI tools into their scientific toolkit and, in doing so, accelerate the pace of materials innovation.

2. AI aided material design

2.1. Computational foundation of modern material design

Computer aided material design matured into well-established field of materials research, which can design new materials, predict material properties and provide structure-based mechanistic insights into material properties. Currently, density functional theory (DFT) is probably

the largest source of relatively standardized, large-scale, and high-quality datasets for subsequent ML (whether in the form of databases or individual publications), at least when it comes to materials research [29]. A plethora of various tools have been developed based on first principles methods, including *ab initio* calculations derived from wavefunction theory or DFT, semiempirical up to empirical (also known as force field) methods. These methods are based on various levels of approximations used to solve Schrödinger equation, which determine their predictive power and also associated computer costs. Particularly the widely used DFT methods enabling access to a wide range of material physical and chemical properties are inherently computationally demanding, often requiring extensive processing time and resources.

Over the past decades, various flavors of DFT functionals have been developed following two major trends, i.e., increasing the predictive power and reducing the computer costs. Such effort is however frameworked by physical principles posing certain limits, which cannot be overcome without compromising quality of the DFT method. Inclusion of non-local electron-electron correlation effects (NLEECs) responsible for London dispersion forces, [30,31] can serve a prototypical example. The commonly used semi-local functionals based on Local Density Approximation (LDA), Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA), and meta GGA approximations do not cover these effects and, e.g., hybrid, double hybrid, and functionals with non-local core have to be employed, at the expense of computer costs. Two decades ago, a new strategy was suggested to cover NLEECs based on inclusion of empirical correction term [32]. Parameters used in this empirical correction were derived based on optimization procedure utilizing high-level *ab initio* calculations as benchmark data. Similar strategies are used to optimize parameters of semiempirical and empirical methods.

This synergy of DFT and ML has proven especially effective in fields such as nanocatalysis and 2D materials discovery. For instance, high-throughput DFT combined with ML has been used to screen thousands of intermetallic nanoparticle surfaces for CO₂ reduction reaction and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) catalysts, significantly accelerating the identification of promising active sites [33]. Similarly, ML models trained on DFT-calculated databases have enabled the rapid prediction of band gaps in 2D materials, guiding experimental synthesis of new semiconducting nanosheets [34]. The trade-off between accuracy and computational cost across different levels of theory is illustrated in Fig. 3, which also highlights the role of machine learning-based interatomic potentials in extending quantum-level accuracy to larger system sizes and longer timescales.

Fig. 3. Trade-off between accuracy and computational cost across different computational modeling methods, illustrating the role of machine learning in bridging traditional approaches.

2.2. From empirical force fields to machine learning based potentials

Empirical methods, called also force fields or molecular mechanics, are computationally very efficient methods. These methods are rooted in

classical physics, where the complex quantum-mechanical expressions governing atomic interactions are replaced by simplified empirical models. For example, bond lengths and angles are typically described using harmonic potentials, torsional rotations are modeled with

Fig. 4. Comparison of molecular geometries predicted by a machine learning potential (ML, grey) ANI-1ccx [38,39] with respect to geometries obtained by B97D/cc-pVTZ calculations (pink, from [31]) for acetone–coronene and toluene–coronene complexes. Both cases show strong overall agreement, with RMSDs of 0.0045 nm and 0.0338 nm, respectively, capturing key structural features while reflecting differences in interaction complexity. The surrounding color-mapped surface visualizes coordinate differences between the ML and DFT structures, where more intense red regions indicate larger differences. The interaction energies calculated by the ML potential (acetone -9.8 kcal/mol and toluene -13.2 kcal/mol) also agree with those (acetone -7.6 kcal/mol and toluene -11.9 kcal/mol), evaluated at CCSD(T)/CBS level [31]. These results illustrate the capability of ML approaches to reproduce high-level quantum accuracy at a fraction of the computational cost.

truncated Fourier series, electrostatic interactions are approximated by Coulombic forces between atom-centered partial charges, and van der Waals forces are represented by the Lennard-Jones potential [35,36]. Using this approach, the total energy of a material system, as well as atomic forces (i.e., the first derivatives of the energy with respect to atomic position), can be enumerated in a fraction of time with respect to *ab initio* methods. However, the underlying approximations significantly constrain their transferability, often limiting their utilization to limited number of systems and conditions. This situation called for development of a more versatile approach, which can be on one hand computationally very effective, i.e., requiring computer costs comparable with those needed to empirical methods and, on the other hand, offering predictive power comparable with high-end *ab initio* methods (Fig. 4). In response to this challenge, machine learning-based force fields (MLFFs) [37] emerged as a promising solution, offering a balance between speed and accuracy that was previously unattainable with conventional methods. Notably, the term MLFF is more commonly used in the context of molecular systems, whereas MLIP is typically preferred in the materials science community.

MLFFs represent a significant advancement, merging the concepts of classical force fields with ML methodologies to enhance the precision and efficiency of molecular simulations. This combination allows computers to deliver more accurate simulation results, often in the same or even shorter timeframes compared to traditional approaches. The core idea is to use ML algorithms to learn the complex relationships between atomic configurations and their corresponding energies and forces, typically by training on extensive datasets generated from high-accuracy quantum mechanical calculations. Once these relationships are learned, the ML model effectively creates a highly detailed map of the potential energy surface (PES). The force field component then utilizes this learned model to calculate the atomic forces, guiding their movement and interactions during simulations to accurately predict molecular behavior and properties [26,37,40,41].

Table 1 summarizes various ML methods, highlighting their key features, applications, advantages, and relevant references. However, it is important to note that many listed methods were primarily developed for molecular rather than materials applications. Specifically, ML methods explicitly designed for large-scale and solid-state materials simulations, often involving crystalline structures, include PhysNet,

M3GNet, MACE, and Behler-Parrinello networks. Nevertheless, the remaining molecular-focused methods provide valuable inspiration for future developments in materials science, as each ML technique offers unique advantages and capabilities that can potentially enhance or complement existing approaches.

A range of ML methods (Table 1) are driving significant progress in chemical simulations and molecular modeling. Each ML approach addresses distinct computational challenges and offers unique advantages: NNs deliver robust, scalable, and highly accurate predictions of molecular energies [42–47]; Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) decipher geometric features to interpret complex molecular structures and dynamics [43,45–48]; Kernel methods provide reliability with well-defined uncertainty estimates [41,49]; and Gradient-domain ML (GDML) ensures rigorous physical consistency [41]. Equivariant NNs and Message-passing neural networks (MPNNs) notably extend these capabilities by incorporating fundamental physical symmetries and modeling multi-body interactions with high fidelity [42–46,48]. Emerging approaches such as Generative models are enabling *de novo* molecule discovery [51], while ACE methods offer fine-grained control over multiscale interaction complexity [45]. The integration of Geodesic and Euclidean information into descriptor optimization highlights the evolving sophistication of representations, aiming for richer, energetically informed molecular descriptors [52].

Collectively, these methodologies signify a step forward in computational chemistry, enhancing accuracy, interpretability, and efficiency across a broad spectrum of chemical applications and materials systems. These advances have also led to the development of practical software tools that implement MLFFs. Most MLFFs are available through dedicated software environments. For instance, the Gaussian Approximation Potential (GAP) [49] is part of the QUantum mechanics and Interatomic Potentials (QUIP) package and demonstrates the versatility of MLIPs in modeling diverse nanomaterials, including amorphous carbon, metal clusters, 2D materials, and porous frameworks [12]. These applications highlight the ability of GAP to capture local structure, mechanical properties, and atomic dynamics with near-DFT accuracy. Another illustrative example of a software tool developed for MLFFs is the MLatom 3 [38], offering ready-to-use implementations of MLFF models for molecular systems and serves as a practical platform for applying many of the concepts discussed above. Currently, several of the most

Table 1

Overview of widely used ML methods in atomistic and materials modeling, including their key features, typical applications, main advantages, and representative examples.

ML Method	Key Features	Applications	Advantages	Examples
NNs (Neural Networks)	Flexible architectures, universal approximators	PES, molecular properties	Highly accurate, scalable, transferable	PhysNetp [42], HIP-NN [43], DeepPot-SE [44], MACE [45], GemNet [46], DTNN [47]
Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)	Message-passing, symmetry-preserving, directional embeddings	Interatomic potentials, molecular dynamics	Explicit geometric information, interpretable	GemNet [46], M3GNet [48], MACE [45], DTNN [47], HIP-NN [43]
Kernel Methods (Gaussian Processes)	Non-parametric, Bayesian uncertainty quantification	Force fields, property prediction	Robust uncertainty estimation, fewer hyperparameters	GAP [49], GDML [41]
High-dimensional NN Potentials (HDNNPs)	NNs incorporating atomic local environments	Atomistic simulations, quantum accuracy	Highly efficient, local and global interaction aware	Behler-Parrinello networks [50], DeepPot-SE [44], HIP-NN [43]
Gradient-Domain ML (GDML)	Enforces conservation laws (energy, force consistency)	Molecular force fields, MD simulations	Accurate energy-force consistency, fewer samples required	GDML [41]
Message-passing neural networks (MPNNs)	Hierarchical messages between atoms	Interatomic potentials, molecular dynamics, reactions	Captures multi-body interactions effectively	GemNet [46], PhysNet [42], MACE [45], HIP-NN [43], M3GNet [48]
Equivariant NNs	Rotationally equivariant to physical symmetries	Molecular dynamics, force prediction, energy prediction	Excellent generalization, symmetry-aware models	GemNet [46], MACE [45], DeepPot-SE [44]
Generative Models (Recurrent Networks, Transformers)	Generates novel molecular structures	Drug discovery, molecule optimization	Highly creative, learns chemical space distribution	Reinvent 4 AI [51]
Atomic Cluster Expansion (ACE)	Systematic expansions of many-body interactions	Efficient and accurate force fields	Precise control over interaction complexity	MACE [45]
Geodesic-Euclidean Descriptor Optimization	Integrates geometric and energetic information	Descriptor design, enhanced representation	Enhanced physical richness and descriptor fidelity	Descriptor Optimization by Iyer & Rubenstein [52]

widely used NN-based force fields, such as ANI [53], DeepMD [54], NequIP [55], and MACE [45], have been incorporated into popular simulation packages like OpenMM and LAMMPS. However, their integration is not included in standard distributions; these functionalities typically require additional modules or plugin packages and must be explicitly compiled or installed by the user. In addition, both ANI and MACE can be used directly via Python interfaces built on PyTorch, such as TorchANI and the MACE GitHub package. These implementations are typically lightweight, GPU-accelerated, straightforward to install, and require minimal compilation skills, making them highly accessible for rapid prototyping, small-scale simulations, or property prediction tasks. Table 2 provides a summary of the models available within MLatom 3, specifying each model's training data, target properties, supported elements, special features, accuracy, limitations, and relevant references. Importantly, none of these models are explicitly designed for materials applications, highlighting a significant opportunity and underscoring the existing gap in this research area. Nevertheless, these molecular-oriented models serve as valuable inspiration for future development in materials-specific ML methodologies. For instance, ANI-2x, though originally trained on small organic molecules, has been successfully employed to model CO₂ adsorption and diffusion in covalent organic frameworks (COFs), demonstrating its surprising transferability to porous nanomaterials and supporting its potential as a bridge between molecular and materials regimes [56].

In parallel, MACE-based force fields, which were developed with materials applications in mind, have already been applied to simulate the mechanical response of graphene oxide under stress, revealing structure-property relationships governed by chemical functionalization [57]. More broadly, MACE has proven effective in several other nanomaterials contexts. For instance, it was used to develop an accurate force field for predicting phonon properties in metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), enabling high-throughput thermal property screening beyond the limits of traditional DFT [58]. MACE has also been applied to model amorphous carbon, demonstrating improved force prediction accuracy compared to earlier ML architectures and showing promise for handling structural complexity in disordered nanoscale systems [59]. These examples signal a growing convergence of ML force field development with real-world materials modeling needs, setting the stage for broader

adoption in nanomaterials research. Extending this trend, a recent comprehensive study showed that transferable MACE-based force fields (MACE-OFF) for organic molecules can deliver *ab initio*-level accuracy across diverse condensed-phase and molecular benchmarks while remaining computationally efficient, underscoring their practicality for real-world materials modeling [60]. All these developments have culminated in the introduction of the MACE foundation model for atom-based materials chemistry (MACE-MP-0), trained once on a broad, chemically diverse dataset and capable of running stable molecular dynamics for both molecules and materials out of the box. Because it can be fine-tuned with only a handful of system-specific configurations, MACE-MP-0 provides not just a tool for specialized studies but a broadly applicable starting point for accelerated and democratized atomistic simulation, setting the stage for future research where fast, reliable, and data-efficient modeling is essential [61].

2.3. On-the-fly parameter optimization

Classical ML methods often achieve predictive accuracy comparable to DFT simulations. Nevertheless, the precision of these models can be further improved by employing "on-the-fly" parameter optimization, a process wherein model parameters are adaptively refined during simulation runs to continually minimize prediction error of the MMFFs. In contemporary practice, certain non-ML computational tools such as the Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (VASP) already incorporate analogous adaptive optimization capabilities. However, the current focus is explicitly on MLFFs, which represent an intermediate strategy bridging conventional DFT and pure ML methodologies. Specifically, MLFFs leverage adaptive learning strategies where, upon encountering configurations that yield predictions exceeding predefined error thresholds, the molecular structures are subjected to explicit DFT calculations. The results from these high-accuracy computations subsequently inform parameter updates within the ML model. This hybridized approach significantly reduces systematic error, thereby achieving enhanced accuracy and computational efficiency compared to classical DFT approaches. Nonetheless, due to the intermittent reliance on DFT calculations, such adaptive MLFFs operate with greater computational overhead relative to purely ML-driven approaches. Numerous studies

Table 2
Limitations, properties and features of ML models available in MLatom3.

Model	Training Data	Target Properties	Supported Elements	Special Features and Accuracy	Limitations	References
ANI-1	20 million DFT energies (ωB97X/6-31 G)	Energies, forces	C, O, H, N	Employs Normal Mode Sampling; accelerates calculations	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[53]
ANI-1x	5 million DFT energies	Energies, forces	C, O, H, N	Active learning, improved accuracy, better unseen system performance	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[38,39,62,63]
ANI-1x-D4	ANI-1x with D4 dispersion correction	Noncovalent interactions	C, O, H, N	Enhances robustness and accuracy without extra computational cost	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[38,64]
ANI-1ccx	0.5 million geometries	High-level coupled-cluster accuracy	C, O, H, N	Up to nine orders faster than classical DFT	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[39]
ANI-1xnr	Reactive molecular database	Reaction pathways, transition states	C, O, H, N	Specialized for reaction simulation, significantly faster MD	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[65]
ANI-2x	ANI-1 data plus torsion profiles	Energies, torsion profiles	C, O, H, N, S, F, Cl	Extended elements, accurate torsion predictions	Limited extended element scope	[66]
ANI-2x-D4	ANI-2x with D4 dispersion correction	Noncovalent interactions	C, O, H, N, S, F, Cl	Includes D4 dispersion for improved noncovalent interactions	Limited extended element scope	[64,66]
AIQM1	ODM2 Hamiltonian, NN & D4 corrections	Coupled-cluster-level accuracy	C, O, H, N	Ensemble NN averaging for robustness, scalability	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[38,67]
AIQM2	GFN2-xTB*, NN & D4 corrections	Transition states, reaction barriers	C, O, H, N	Enhanced accuracy for transitions and barriers, transfer learning	Restricted to C, O, H, N	[68]
DM21	ML-augmented DFT	Single-point calculations	All main-group elements	Addresses fractional electron/spin issues	Limited to single-point calculations	[69]
AIMNet2	Extensive ML dataset	General molecular properties	C, O, H, N, B, F, Si, P, S, Cl, As, Se, Br, I	Accuracy comparable to DFT	None mentioned	[70]
UAIQM (Framework)	Integrated classical & ML methods	Broad applicability and accuracy	Diverse elements	Updatable, user data integrated, dynamic model selection, uncertainty quantification	None explicitly mentioned	[71]
OMNI-P2x	ANI-1ccx and PubChemQC datasets	Excited states simulations	H, C, N, O, F, S, Cl	Universal potential mainly for excited states simulations; TD-DFT accuracy	Restricted to H, C, N, O, F, S, Cl	[72]

have documented the efficacy and practical implementations of these hybrid methodologies, as highlighted extensively within the referenced literature [13,73–81].

2.4. Applications, predictive power and challenges of MLFFs

Trained MLFFs can efficiently predict energy minima of structures, offering accuracy of advanced *ab initio* methods at a fraction of the computational cost. This makes them particularly well suited for rapid geometry optimization and structure screening. They can also be used as computationally inexpensive alternatives for MD simulations, enabling the exploration of long time scales or large systems that would be otherwise impractical with traditional quantum methods [37]. Interestingly, some MLFFs can even predict transition states of molecules when trained on suitable high-energy configurations [82]. Beyond structural and dynamic modeling, certain ML-based approaches have demonstrated strong predictive capabilities for critical material properties such as electronic band gaps, thermal conductivities and absorption energies - properties traditionally out of reach for classical force fields [83,84].

These predictive strengths also support inverse material design. By explicitly defining target properties, ML models can inversely generate molecular structures or materials tailored to meet specific functional requirements [85,86]. Such predictive and generative tasks have substantial implications for synthesis planning and optimization, streamlining experimental workflows and enhancing synthesis efficiency and effectiveness [87]. Utilization of MLFFs can significantly reduce trial-and-error experimentation, thus conserving resources and accelerating development timelines. Moreover, many ML models inherently facilitate the quantification of their prediction uncertainties, which is a critical feature that provides researchers with confidence estimates, enabling more informed decision-making and highlighting potential risks associated with model outcomes [13]. The integration of uncertainty quantification significantly enhances the reliability and interpretability of ML based approaches in materials research. However, the growing number of specialized models presents a challenge in selecting the most appropriate one for a given application. Recent trends in the development of biomolecular force fields, which have evolved over several decades, suggest a clear shift toward specialization rather than unification into a single, universally applicable model [88]. A similar trajectory is likely for MLFFs, despite ongoing efforts to design general-purpose frameworks. An alternative pathway could be the establishment of foundation models that can be fine-tuned for specific tasks. In either case, users must be well informed about the intended scope and training domain of a given MLFF to ensure its appropriate application. This underscores the importance of standardized benchmarking datasets that enable robust and transparent evaluation of model performance across material classes and property regimes. The lack of such prior knowledge regarding the utility and reliability of particular MLFFs remains a barrier to their widespread adoption in computer simulations, which is a challenge that could be alleviated through AI-driven agents, as discussed later in this chapter.

Another major limitation of MLIPs is their restricted transferability. Whereas the preceding section emphasized increasing specialization of force fields, transferability raises the complementary issue of whether training data generated for one model can be reused by another. This is particularly relevant in the era of open data policies, where high-quality MLIP datasets are increasingly available but often tied to a specific algorithm. Niblett et al. [89] systematically examined this question using organic carbonate electrolytes (used in electrochemical energy storage devices) as a test case, comparing how training data curated for a GAP model transfer to two different architectures: the feedforward neural-network DeePMD and the equivariant message-passing framework MACE. Their analysis revealed several key insights. First, configurations designed by human intuition to address systematic deficiencies (e.g., volume-scan data probing density variations) transfer robustly

across architectures, whereas iterative configurations generated by active learning with GAP provided little benefit to DeePMD. Second, MACE models proved markedly more robust and data-efficient; even with relatively small and simple training sets, they delivered stable trajectories and accurate liquid-state properties, while DeePMD required significantly larger and more carefully augmented datasets to avoid instabilities. These findings suggest that transferable training data are not algorithm-agnostic (some are broadly useful, while others remain highly model-specific) and that message-passing models such as MACE hold distinct advantages in terms of generalization and data reuse. More broadly, the study underscores that dataset diversity and quality are more critical than algorithm-specific fine-tuning, and that community-curated training corpora could substantially accelerate progress. The field is now moving toward transferable ML potentials and even foundational models that can be fine-tuned with small amounts of system-specific data, potentially combining the robustness of architectures like MACE with the efficiency of shared datasets [60,90,91].

Noncovalent interactions (including, e.g., London dispersion forces, dipole-dipole interactions (Keesom forces) and polarization effects, which are often collectively referred as van der Waals interactions) play also an important role in materials science. They typically act over longer distances (exceeding ~ 0.3 nm) compared to covalent bonds (~ 0.1 – 0.25 nm), and their interaction energies are two to three orders of magnitude lower. Despite their relative weakness, they underpin key phenomena such as molecular crystal packing, interfacial adsorption, and supramolecular self-assembly. Accurate representation of non-covalent forces remains a challenge for many MLFFs and MLIPs. Most currently available models are not explicitly trained to capture these interactions with high fidelity. Although specialized models exist that target particular material classes, such as graphene and related systems, they are not broadly transferable across diverse material domains [92]. More general MLFF frameworks can, in principle, describe noncovalent interactions, but this typically requires retraining on datasets in which such interactions are explicitly represented. An alternative strategy involves the incorporation of empirical dispersion corrections, most commonly the D4 scheme, which has been shown to systematically improve the accuracy of MLFF predictions for systems governed by noncovalent interactions [64]. In this context, it should be noted that electrostatic interactions, which are involved in many important phenomena such as ionic crystal stability, biomaterials, solvation, and electrode processes, represent another challenge due to their slow decay and inherently long-range character. The explicit inclusion of long-range electrostatics, for example through the particle-mesh Ewald (PME) method [93], has been shown to significantly improve the accuracy of molecular simulations of polyanionic biomolecules such as nucleic acids [94].

AI is also beginning to lower barriers in computational chemistry making an additional interface layer between a user and computational tool. Recently, Dral et al. [95] introduced a platform that integrates a conversational chatbot interface with advanced simulation tools, enabling users to obtain results directly from simple, user-defined queries. This work highlights the potential of LLMs and agent-based systems to democratize access to computational methods. In materials science, such approaches could allow non-specialists to perform complex simulations and analyses with minimal training, thereby reducing entry barriers and expanding participation in AI-assisted research activities.

2.5. Machine-Learning potentials for single-atom catalysts: current capabilities and perspectives

MLIPs are transforming the study of single-atom catalysts (SACs) by bridging the gap between quantum-mechanical accuracy and large-scale simulations. These approaches facilitate a more efficient exploration of catalytic stability, structure-activity relationships, and reaction energetics, helping to narrow down broad compositional landscapes that

would otherwise be prohibitively expensive to study solely with traditional QM methods. By capturing complex atomic interactions at reduced computational cost, ML potentials not only guide rational catalyst design but also complement experimental efforts, improving the prediction of performance and selectivity. Their growing adoption highlights a shift toward data-driven workflows that combine accuracy, speed, and scalability, paving the way for more systematic and informed discovery of next-generation SACs.

A hybrid DFT-ML framework was developed to design SAC for nitrogen reduction reaction (NRR) by combining quantum calculations on 126 SAC candidates with ML models trained on simple electronic descriptors [96]. The study introduced the bidirectional activation mechanism, linking specific electronic properties of the metal atom to catalytic activity. ML predictions accurately captured activity, selectivity, and stability trends. Tamtaji et al. [97] used a range of ML approaches to establish structure-activity relationships for SACs in key electrochemical reactions (such as hydrogen evolution, HER, oxygen reduction, ORR, oxygen evolution, OER, nitrogen reduction reaction, NRR, etc.). Their study identified critical descriptors, including d-electron count, oxide formation enthalpy, ionization energy, and Bader charge, that govern adsorption and reaction free energies on SAC-support systems. In a recent study, ML combined with DFT calculations was employed to screen over 10,000 single-atom alloy (SAA) surfaces for methane cracking activity, identifying key descriptors such as dopant surface energy and d-electron configuration that govern C–H bond activation barriers [98]. The ML-guided workflow enabled the selection of promising Ir/Ni and Re/Ni catalysts, which were subsequently validated experimentally, demonstrating high hydrogen yield, excellent selectivity, and improved stability under mechanochemical conditions. A recent study combined DFT-generated datasets with ML models to investigate the stability and activity of transition-metal-doped MXenes as SACs for ORR and OER [99]. By combining DFT-generated data with convolutional NN models, the approach enabled rapid screening of numerous candidate surfaces, identifying Ni-Ti₃C₂S₂ and Cu-Ti₃C₂S₂ as promising low-overpotential catalysts. This study showcases ML-accelerated materials discovery, where ML significantly reduced the computational workload needed to assess catalyst stability and reaction energetics across a broad set of MXene-based candidates. A related study extended ML applications beyond catalysis, using literature-derived datasets and regression models to predict the optical properties of red and near-infrared emitting carbon dots (CDs) based on their synthesis parameters [100]. This approach demonstrated how ML can capture links between synthesis conditions and functional properties, reducing trial-and-error experimentation during synthesis optimization. Similarly, interpretable ML models have been developed to predict atomic-scale magnetic anisotropy in quantum materials, enabling rapid screening of transition-metal dimers on defective graphene and supported substrates based on cost-effective DFT data [8]. It should be noted that the field of SAC would significantly benefit from AI-driven tools, which could tackle the complexity of various SACs and introduce more rational approach to this so far very empirical field. Particularly important would be to delineate relationships between stability and activity of catalytic centers of SACs [101].

Overall, the mentioned studies highlight both the opportunities and challenges in applying ML to new materials discovery. While limitations such as restricted data availability and the need for experimental validation remain common, recent research demonstrates that ML-accelerated materials discovery can streamline candidate screening, reveal fundamental links between structure and performance, and support the design of improved materials with significantly reduced computational and experimental effort. By integrating data-driven models with high-level quantum calculations, these approaches enable a more systematic, scalable, and informed exploration of complex material spaces, facilitating the design of materials with tailored properties.

3. Synthesis supported by AI

Besides material design AI has become a powerful tool in chemical synthesis, enabling advancements from synthesis planning, via reaction conditions optimization, up to autonomous laboratories. AI offers new strategies for pathway prediction, materials discovery, and the automation of experimental processes. First, we provide brief overview of AI-tools developed for organic synthesis, because many so far developed concepts are inspiring for material science. It should be mentioned that in organic synthesis the molecules can be represented by rather simple and straightforward representations (based, e.g., on structural formula, 3D structures, SMILES, SELFIES, and fingerprints). Unlike molecules, materials are more complex, and their representations vary depending on the type of material, the level of description (atomic, structural, or functional), and the task (e.g., property prediction, phase classification, generative design). While there has not been established a single unified and widely accepted representation for materials yet, models like MEGNet (developed by Materials Virtual Lab) [102] and Roost by Goodall and Lee [103] are worth mentioning. The trend is toward hybrid, flexible frameworks that adapt to the available data (structure, composition, processing) and use powerful models like GNNs and transformers to bridge across domains. However, most traditional materials representations, especially those designed for bulk, periodic solids, do not work well for nanomaterials or atomically precise systems (including, e.g., SACs). However, multiple efforts are now addressing this gap [104,105].

3.1. AI tools in organic synthesis

AI models entered the domain of chemical synthesis and so far developed tools of computer-assisted synthesis planning (CASP) [106] demonstrated successful application not only in organic synthesis and retrosynthesis, but also in material science. In organic chemistry, retrosynthesis refers to the strategy of designing the synthesis of large molecules by working backward from the target compound to simpler precursors. Various AI tools showed strong predictive performance in retrosynthetic analysis, surpassing traditional computer-aided search methods [20]. Recently, Zhang et al. [81] proposed a neurosymbolic framework [107] that combined symbolic reasoning, such as rule-based retrosynthesis steps, with NNs capable of recognizing complex patterns. This approach enabled more efficient learning from synthetic patterns and significantly expanded the available reaction template libraries. The prediction of organic synthesis is a challenging and important task in organic chemistry, attracting sustained attention for several decades. The availability of curate reaction databases (e.g., Beilstein database), along with the development of automatized tools for information extraction from literature (e.g., ChemDataExtractor [108]) facilitated the construction of training datasets that fueled the development of AI-driven tools in this field. Sun and David recently provided a critical and authoritative overview of text-mining approaches in materials synthesis, highlighting both the potential and current limitations of automated data extraction from scientific literature [109]. Fingerprint-based NN algorithms achieved high accuracy in reaction type classification using only reactants and reagents as input. These models outperformed rule-based systems in terms of flexibility and scalability, as they could adapt to new reaction types through the simple addition of data to the training set, rather than requiring manual encoding of new mechanistic rules [110]. The IBM RXN platform (accessible via a web interface) employed the Molecular Transformer model [111], which was trained on the large Science of Synthesis (SOS) database and achieved forward reaction prediction accuracy exceeding 90 %. Another important area of synthesis where AI has proven useful is in the optimization of reaction conditions. Shields and coworkers developed a software tool based on Bayesian optimization algorithms that required fewer iterations than a human researcher to identify optimal conditions [112]. Such methods helped reduce resource

consumption, enhance yields and selectivity [113,114]. Further discussion and a broader overview of AI applications in organic synthesis can be found in a recent dedicated review [115].

3.2. Materials synthesis driven by AI

Building on advances in organic synthesis, AI is now playing an increasingly important role in materials synthesis, although the shift is far from straightforward. While molecular systems benefit from well-defined representations, materials present unique challenges. Their structures span a range of dimensionalities and ordering, from periodic crystals to amorphous solids and nanostructures, and their synthetic accessibility often depends on complex thermodynamic landscapes, kinetic constraints, and processing environments. Furthermore, materials (particularly nanomaterials) synthesis involves a broader set of routes, which can be categorized into bottom-up approaches (e.g., solvothermal synthesis, chemical vapor deposition, molecular assembly) and top-down strategies (e.g., milling, lithography, exfoliation). Each pathway requires distinct planning tools, input formats, and experimental parameters. Although AI models developed for molecules offer valuable architectural and conceptual blueprints, direct translation to materials requires tailoring both representations and objectives. For example, synthesis of extended solids depends not only on target stoichiometry and bonding patterns, but also on phase stability, support interactions, and defect tolerance, i.e., features poorly captured by SMILES or fingerprint descriptors. This complexity has inspired the creation of specialized AI frameworks for materials synthesis, some of which already show promise.

Several AI-driven platforms have emerged to address these needs. The Synthesis Process Encoder-Decoder (SPENDE) NN [116] represents a modular approach to synthesis prediction. It incorporates graph-based encoders to analyze input structures, sequence decoders to generate procedural steps, and NNs to optimize experimental parameters. By combining structural analysis with language generation, SPENDE produces interpretable synthesis protocols, thereby narrowing the gap between computational planning and laboratory execution. On the discovery front, the Computational Autonomy for Materials Discovery (CAMD) framework [117] integrated DFT calculations with active learning to propose stable inorganic materials. However, CAMD's experimental validation was limited, as only one out of six predicted oxide phases were successfully synthesized, exposing critical limitations in AI-driven discovery, such as its difficulty in accounting for kinetic barriers and synthetic accessibility.

To improve reliability, active learning, uncertainty quantification, and feedback loops with autonomous labs, enabling iterative refinement of predictions based on experimental outcomes is explored as described in following subchapter. For example, platforms like the Open Catalyst Project (OC20, OC22) [16,118] form massive datasets for surface-catalyst interactions and support GNN models capable of predicting reaction energetics in realistic environments, including SAC and low-symmetry surfaces [119]. These trends are also emphasized in the recent review by Lv et al. [120], which focuses on AI-assisted synthesis of MXenes. The paper catalogs the key synthetic strategies for this class of materials and emphasizes how AI can aid in navigating this complex chemical landscape. Four major synthesis pathways are highlighted: selective etching, chemical vapor deposition, bottom-up strategies like template-assisted growth, and molten salt synthesis. Each route presents distinct challenges in terms of precursor selection, reaction kinetics, and surface terminations. The authors stress the role of ML in predicting optimal reaction parameters, tailoring etching conditions, and even controlling termination groups, which remain notoriously difficult to tune. Moreover, the review calls for the creation of structured datasets specific to MXene synthesis to facilitate model training and reproducibility. By aligning predictive modeling with experimentally validated synthesis protocols, this approach complements the broader push toward AI-integrated materials discovery, emphasizing that

domain-specific knowledge remains critical to the practical success of generative models and autonomous synthesis frameworks.

Another demonstration of AI-assisted synthesis planning and property prediction is presented by Tuchin et al. [100]. They addressed the challenge of synthesizing CDs with emission in the red and near-infrared (NIR) spectral regions, which is an important goal for bioimaging and photonics. They curated a dataset of 127 syntheses from 110 publications, covering variations in precursors, solvents, synthesis methods, and conditions. They applied both human-driven and machine-driven clustering to categorize CDs based on chemical origin and optical response, and trained multiple linear regression (LR) and K-nearest neighbor (KNN) models to predict absorption maxima, photoluminescence peak positions, and photoluminescence quantum yield. Importantly, their model was validated through experiments conducted in three independent laboratories, demonstrating that optical properties could be predicted within <20 nm accuracy for photoluminescence peaks and with $\sim\pm 5\%$ precision in quantum yields. This study illustrates the growing maturity of forward synthesis-property models for nanomaterials and reinforces the importance of structured, multi-lab datasets and interpretable models. The open-source code and dataset made publicly available by the authors provide a template for further AI-driven work in nanocarbon photonics and related fields.

Finally, advances in generative models, such as graph-based variational autoencoders and transformer architectures, are being explored to propose novel inorganic compositions and their plausible synthesis routes. These methods aim not only to generate stable structures but also to integrate synthesis constraints from the outset [121,122]. Taken together, these efforts demonstrate that while AI models for materials synthesis can build upon the foundations laid in organic chemistry, they must be fundamentally adapted to reflect the structural complexity, multi-scale nature, and often non-equilibrium conditions of materials formation. Future progress will rely on combining data-driven predictions with physically informed models and autonomous experimentation to accelerate the development of novel materials.

3.3. Material discovery driven by AI

AI-based tools hold tremendous promise in the discovery of new materials. The Graph Networks for Materials Exploration (GNoME) project [123], as a prototypical example, predicts key properties such as formation energy and stability using advanced ML models. It employs two complementary frameworks: the first generates candidate materials by modifying known crystal structures, while the second predicts stability based solely on reduced chemical formulas. In the first framework, new crystals are created through symmetry-aware partial substitutions (SAPS) and random search strategies. SAPS systematically replaces atomic sites while preserving crystal symmetry, enabling efficient and comprehensive exploration of substitutional derivatives. To enhance novelty and prioritise discovery, the substitution probabilities are adjusted, significantly expanding the range of viable substitutions. GNoME filters generated materials using volume-based test-time augmentation and uncertainty quantification via deep ensembles. In the second framework, compositional models assess stability without structural information. The input consists only of reduced chemical formulas. Since traditional oxidation-state balancing can be overly restrictive and may exclude valid compounds such as $\text{Li}_{15}\text{Si}_4$, the method relaxes constraints to accommodate broader compositional space. After filtering with GNoME, each selected composition is initialized with 100 random structures and evaluated using *ab initio* random structure searching (AIRSS). Across both frameworks, candidate materials are first screened by GNN ensembles and subsequently validated with DFT calculations. The results are used to iteratively retrain the models through active learning, improving accuracy and generalisation. This approach led to the prediction of over 2.2 million novel crystal structures, with approximately 380,000 identified as stable or near the convex hull. Of these, hundreds have been independently synthesized,

supporting the reliability of GNoME's predictions. This large-scale effort has produced an extensive and diverse library of stable materials, including candidates for batteries, superconductors, and other advanced technologies, marking a significant advance in AI-assisted materials discovery.

However, several outcomes of the GNoME project have been subject to critical evaluation, highlighting key challenges that must be addressed to fully realize the promise of AI-driven materials discovery. One major concern is the neglect of entropy-driven disorder in high-temperature synthesis, which significantly influences phase stability. Because GNoME's predictions rely on DFT calculations at 0 K, they often favor ordered atomic configurations that may not persist at synthesis temperatures, potentially leading to unrealistic structures. Many predicted compounds involve improbable ordering of chemically similar elements, such as rare-earth or transition-metal cations, that are experimentally known to form disordered solid solutions. This artificial ordering frequently results in symmetry-lowered crystal structures that do not reflect thermodynamically favored phases. While GNoME has generated hundreds of thousands of thermodynamically plausible compositions, their utility, functionality, and experimental viability remain unverified. Thus, many of the predicted entries may not qualify as "new materials" in a practical sense. To improve the scientific impact of such AI-based approaches, it is essential to integrate deeper knowledge of solid-state chemistry, experimental constraints, and synthesis feasibility, alongside a more rigorous definition of what constitutes a truly novel and functional material [124].

Materials Project database has been used by Sendek et al. [125] to accelerate the discovery of solid lithium-ion conductors using ML. From over 12,000 materials, roughly 300 candidates were selected based on thermodynamic phase stability, low electronic conduction, high electrochemical stability, and exclusion of transition metals. Their ML model employed a gradient-boosted decision tree (GBDT) algorithm trained on ionic conductivity data, achieving a 10-fold acceleration over manual screening. ML models narrowed this list to 19 best candidates, validated alongside 21 randomly chosen materials through DFT molecular dynamics. The model demonstrated a faster and more systematic approach to identifying promising materials compared to conventional human-driven workflows, highlighting its potential to reduce bias and accelerate high-throughput screening. However, its performance relies exclusively on computational data, and the limited integration of experimental validation remains a key challenge. The authors noted that the model outperformed Ph.D. students in material discovery. This highlights the potential of AI to reduce human bias in high-throughput screening, though the dataset's reliance on computational (not experimental) data remains a limitation.

A generative diffusion model for inverse inorganic materials design (named MatterGen) that overcomes several limitations of prior approaches has been recently introduced by Zeni et al. [121]. Unlike conventional screening or substitution-based methods, MatterGen directly generates stable, diverse, and novel crystal structures across the periodic table while allowing precise control over target properties such as composition, symmetry, magnetic density, bandgap, and mechanical strength. Trained on over 600,000 DFT-verified structures, the model employs a joint diffusion process to iteratively denoise atom types, coordinates, and lattices, yielding structures that are more than twice as likely to be stable, unique, and new compared to previous models. MatterGen also demonstrates remarkable generalization by rediscovering over 2000 known but unseen experimental structures and validating one generated material (TaCr_2O_6) experimentally, with measured bulk modulus within 20 % of the target value. Its ability to generate low-supply-chain-risk magnets and high-performance materials under multiple constraints positions MatterGen as a useful tool for data-driven materials discovery.

AI4Mater framework, developed in the last decade, offers a comprehensive and modular ecosystem designed to address critical bottlenecks in AI-assisted materials discovery by combining data

infrastructure, domain expertise, and collaborative tools under a unified architecture. The framework emphasizes the need for reproducibility, transparency, and interpretability, proposing four core pillars: high-quality open datasets, ML pipelines, knowledge graphs, and open benchmarking protocols. AI4Mater tackles the heterogeneity of materials data through standardized ontologies and metadata formats, while also supporting uncertainty quantification and model validation workflows which is an often-overlooked aspect in existing generative and predictive models. By incorporating FAIR principles and community-driven curation, AI4Mater offers a viable platform for a scalable and sustainable AI-powered materials innovation ecosystem. Its integration with autonomous labs and human-in-the-loop workflows also bridges discovery with practical implementation, making it highly relevant for next-generation platforms in materials synthesis and design [126].

A generative AI framework based on molecular diffusion modeling was developed to design high-performing MOFs for carbon capture [127]. By combining linkers extracted from known MOFs with selected metal nodes, the model generated new cubic MOF candidates. A diffusion probabilistic model was used to sample diverse linkers, prioritizing those with high binding affinity and thermal stability. However, many generated structures initially lacked pore connectivity, which is a critical feature for MOFs, as their performance in applications such as gas separation and storage strongly depends on the accessibility and continuity of their internal porosity. This limitation was mitigated by refining the metal node selection process, which improved interlinker compatibility and overall framework integrity. Candidate structures were further screened using Grand Canonical Monte Carlo simulations for stability and Crystal Graph Convolutional NNs to predict CO_2 adsorption performance. The resulting framework proved efficient and cost-effective in producing viable MOF designs, underscoring the growing potential of generative AI in accelerating the discovery of nanoporous materials with tunable porosity and targeted properties [128]. Similarly, AI was applied to design supported ionic liquid membranes (SILMs) for CO_2 capture, traditionally developed through costly trial-and-error experiments. Using a dataset of experimentally tested SILMs and their CO_2 adsorption data, a GAN was trained to propose new membrane formulations [129]. The model uncovered relationships between operational conditions (pressure, temperature, molecular weight) and adsorption capacity, and could also predict long-term membrane stability. Top-performing AI-generated SILMs were synthesized and tested, validating the model's utility. However, discrepancies between predicted and actual performance under extreme pressures highlighted areas for further refinement.

The perspectives of material synthesis have been recently broadened by Jiang and coworkers [130], who overviewed AI-assisted design, synthesis, and analysis of smart biomaterials. While focused on biomedical applications, many of the challenges and opportunities they describe, such as the need for multimodal data integration, generative design under biological constraints, and the real-time coupling of sensing and adaptive behavior, are equally relevant to all materials. The review introduces frameworks that combine structure-property prediction, multi-objective optimization, and experiment-in-the-loop approaches to develop stimuli-responsive hydrogels, implantable sensors, and drug delivery platforms. Notably, the authors emphasize the growing role of diffusion models and reinforcement learning in navigating complex design spaces, and they stress the importance of feedback-rich environments to fine-tune both functionality and synthetic accessibility.

AI-driven materials discovery has made significant progress by combining graph-based predictive models, generative frameworks, and increasingly sophisticated synthesis planning. Whether in the design of energy materials (e.g., GNoME, MatterGen), low-dimensional systems (e.g., MXenes), or biologically responsive platforms, common principles emerge. The integration of domain-specific constraints, curated datasets, interpretable models, and feedback from experiment is essential. Moreover, generative models are only as valuable as their connection to

realistic synthetic routes, and experimental validation remains the cornerstone of genuine material innovation. Future progress will thus depend on unified frameworks that incorporate high-quality data, scalable experimentation, and human oversight enabling AI not to replace but to accelerate and elevate the process of materials discovery.

3.4. Autonomous laboratories

The concept of autonomous laboratories has evolved over the past two decades from simple robotic arms and autosamplers toward increasingly sophisticated, integrated platforms capable of designing, executing, and analyzing experiments with minimal human intervention. Initially developed to increase throughput and reproducibility in pharmaceutical and analytical chemistry workflows, these systems entered to cutting-edge research in materials science and synthetic chemistry. The penetration of AI into autonomous laboratories has transformed them from passive automation tools into adaptive, decision-making systems. AI enables the autonomous lab to not only perform predefined experiments but also to design and optimize new synthetic pathways, analyze data in real time, and refine experimental strategies through closed-loop feedback (Fig. 5). Key benefits include accelerated discovery, enhanced resource efficiency, and the ability to explore complex, high-dimensional design spaces that would be almost inaccessible through manual approaches. AI thus acts as a catalyst for transforming traditional lab work into a self-driving, hypothesis-generating process, paving the way for discoveries that are faster and more

reproducible. Building on vehicle autonomy concepts, six graded levels of laboratory autonomy (L0–L5) [131] have been proposed (see the bottom panel of the Fig. 5 for more details), yet high levels of automation (L3 and above) are still rare. In practice, human oversight continues to play a critical role providing validation, ensuring safety, and guiding strategic decision-making [132]. Although autonomous laboratories aspire to complete self-driving capability, expert supervision helps mitigate errors and address unexpected experimental outcomes. Recently, Liu and co-workers offered an insightful perspective on balancing laboratory autonomy with human expertise, highlighting the advantages and drawbacks of a “human-on-the-loop” approach [133]. They emphasized that human adaptability and flexibility enable efficient on-the-fly problem-solving as well as reconfiguration, repair, and cleaning, i.e., tasks that remain challenging for machines. In this respect, near-term development is likely to focus on symbiotic integration, combining the bias-free endurance of robots with the versatility and adaptive judgment of human experts.

Promises of autonomous laboratories must be weighed against significant challenges in practical deployment, such as system complexity, high capital costs, and integration with existing laboratory infrastructure. Chemical and materials synthesis are inherently complex, multi-step processes that typically require dedicated glassware or equipment, careful handling of intermediates, purification, and iterative optimization. Many of these steps, e.g., solid–liquid separations, recrystallization, solvent exchange, or multi-step temperature and pressure programs, just to name a few examples, are extremely

Fig. 5. Schematic of an AI-driven autonomous laboratory integrating inverse design, automated synthesis, and real-time characterization within a closed-loop feedback cycle. The right panel illustrates top-down and bottom-up fabrication pathways converging at the nanoscale, whose inclusion and optimization remains particularly challenging for fully automated workflows. The bottom panel shows the levels of autonomy in laboratory research, adapted from Hung et al. [131], outlining the minimum automation required in each category. Published by the Royal Society of Chemistry under the CC BY-NC 3.0 licence.

challenging to fully automate in a generalizable manner. In addition, there are several critical but often under-reported aspects that strongly impact reproducibility and scalability, including the maintenance of clean conditions, prevention of cross-contamination, and proper waste management. These routine laboratory tasks, rarely described in the scientific literature but indispensable for successful R&D, underscore why the translation of autonomous laboratory concepts from proof-of-principle demonstrations to reliable, broadly deployable platforms remains highly non-trivial.

RoboChem, developed by Slattery and coworkers [134], optimizes photochemical reactions through a closed-loop Bayesian optimization algorithm, reducing the required iterations to achieve optimal reaction conditions significantly compared to traditional grid searches. In this system, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy was used to monitor and optimize reaction outcomes. Similarly, Epps and coworkers [135] launched a platform utilizing AI-driven surrogate models for synthesizing metal halide perovskite quantum dots, achieving high photoluminescence quantum yields while reducing experimental workload. Their approach relied on photoluminescence and absorption spectra to evaluate peak emission, emission linewidth, and quantum yield. Despite its success, the method remains limited by throughput constraints inherent to microfluidic reactors. A notable advancement was made by Berkeley's A-Lab, introduced by Szymanski and coworkers [136], which employed active learning and ML algorithms to synthesize

inorganic compounds based on phase-stability data. Characterization of the synthesized materials was performed using powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), confirming a high synthesis success rate and discovery of numerous novel materials. Despite this, A-Lab encountered challenges in accurately predicting amorphous byproducts and kinetic barriers, illustrating limitations in current AI models. Further enhancing autonomous experimentation, Boiko and coworkers [137] developed Coscientist, a system architecture utilizing GPT-4 modules for precise chemical experimentation. UV/VIS spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) were among the tools for characterization and decision-making. More recently, foundation models, i.e., LLMs with multimodal and reasoning capabilities, have been proposed as cognitive AI cores in self-driving labs. These agents can formulate experimental plans, interface seamlessly with lab hardware, and interpret multimodal outputs (e.g. spectra, images), although challenges remain in precision control and error alignment [138]. To highlight recent progress in this area, Fig. 6 presents examples of autonomous platforms for chemical synthesis and characterization.

AI-driven platforms also demonstrated notable advancements in synthesizing specific materials. Li and coworkers [141] developed CARGO, combining ML and robotics to synthesize horizontally aligned carbon nanotube arrays, significantly outperforming traditional catalysts. Here, the quality and structure of the nanotubes were verified by Raman spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and atomic

Fig. 6. Examples of automated platforms for chemical synthesis and characterization. a) Autonomous inorganic synthesis using DFT, ML-guided synthesis recipe generation, robotic dosing/heating/characterization, and active-learning optimization [136]. Reproduced from Ref. [136] under a CC BY 4.0 International License. b) Robotic flow chemistry system for on-demand organic synthesis with automated reaction planning and execution [106]. Reproduced from Ref. [106] with permission from Science/AAAS. c) RoboChem benchtop platform for self-optimizing photocatalytic transformations [134]. Reproduced from Ref. [134] with permission from Science/AAAS. d) iSynth platform with automated liquid transfer to NMR tubes and NMR-Agent robotic handling for sampling [140]. Reproduced from Ref. [140] under a CC BY 4.0 International License.

force microscopy (AFM). Sabattini and coworkers [142] advanced graphene synthesis using adaptive AI-driven temperature optimization methods, achieving higher uniformity and quality, though the method's reliance on SiC substrates limits broader applicability. Graphene growth was verified using Raman spectroscopy, AFM, XRD and angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES). Environmental sustainability has also benefitted from AI integration. Vu and coworkers [143] demonstrated a greener synthetic route for Zn-HKUST-1 MOFs by using LLMs and high-throughput robotics, efficiently determining optimal synthesis conditions without environmentally harmful reagents. SEM, XRD, and Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy were used to verify material formation and purity. Despite these notable demonstrations, most systems are limited in throughput, generalizability, or scalability. For example, microfluidic reactors restrict sample size, while AI models often fail to account for kinetic barriers or unexpected byproducts. These issues highlight that the transition from proof-of-concept prototypes to robust, general-purpose autonomous laboratories remains far from complete.

Collectively, these advances illustrate AI's substantial yet evolving impact on autonomous laboratories, underscoring continued opportunities and challenges related to accuracy, scalability, and environmental sustainability in chemical synthesis, as well as robustness in complex, multi-step tasks. However, automated, AI-assisted characterization remains comparatively underdeveloped. This lag is largely due to the complexity of extracting reliable, actionable insights from high-dimensional and multimodal data sources, such as spectroscopy, diffraction, and various forms of electron microscopy. Recent progress suggests that this barrier is beginning to erode. For example, foundation models and vision transformers are now being applied to electron micrographs to enable defect classification and atomic structure recognition without extensive preprocessing. Autonomous platforms such as DeepEM and AtomAI have demonstrated high accuracy in detecting lattice distortions and crystal boundaries across large microscopy datasets [144,145]. In XRD, convolutional NNs are being used to classify polymorphs and identify peak shifts indicative of phase transitions [146–151]. These tools not only accelerate data interpretation but can also trigger experimental branching in real-time turning previously static characterization steps into dynamic, decision-making processes within closed-loop workflows. Despite these promising developments, AI-driven characterization remains fragmented, often requiring bespoke pipelines and manual data curation. Integration with robotics, edge processing, and standard lab information systems (LIMS) is still limited, slowing adoption outside specialized facilities. Nevertheless, the coupling of intelligent perception systems with autonomous synthesis is likely to become a cornerstone of next-generation self-driving laboratories.

Still, the broader adoption of autonomous labs faces formidable practical barriers, which include high capital expenditure, system complexity, and limited scalability beyond controlled R&D environments. As highlighted by national initiatives such as the US National Center for Autonomous Materials Science (NIST), overcoming these challenges will require standardized infrastructure, robust software ecosystems, and sustained investment in interdisciplinary training. Without such coordinated efforts, the transformative potential of autonomous laboratories may remain confined to elite research institutions, falling short of their promise to revolutionize material and chemical innovation at scale. In this respect, advances in 3D printing technologies could provide an important impetus for democratizing access to autonomous laboratories by lowering barriers to constructing modular hardware and essential building blocks [152]. Beyond technical capability [153], deploying autonomous labs raises important questions of regulatory compliance, data integrity, and ethical governance. For instance, agencies like FDA and EMA emphasize transparent data pipelines, audit trails, and risk-managed design. Moreover, interdisciplinary experts posit that responsible deployment requires robust data stewardship, open benchmarking, and a human-centric design

ethos.

3.5. Mobile robotics and compact platforms

While large-scale autonomous laboratories have demonstrated remarkable capabilities, their high cost, infrastructural demands, and spatial constraints limit their deployment. To overcome these barriers and enable more democratized access to automation, mobile and compact robotic platforms designed for distributed, flexible, and resource-efficient operation are explored. One example is the mobile robotic chemist developed in Cooper laboratory [21], which autonomously navigated laboratory space and optimized photocatalytic reactions over 688 experiments with minimal human intervention. Equipped with a precision liquid-handling arm ($\pm 0.1 \mu\text{L}$) and Bayesian optimization algorithms, this robot could work 21.6 h per day including autonomous charging and adjusting experiments based on real-time UV/VIS data. Despite some performance degradation due to catalyst instability, the study demonstrated the feasibility of long-duration, AI-guided experimentation without fixed infrastructure. Other systems have adopted a modular approach by splitting laboratory functions. For example, Autonomous Mobile Robots for Exploratory Synthetic Chemistry [140] segmented their architecture into mobile synthesis and stationary analytical units. Samples were transferred between modules and analyzed using NMR and ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS). While effective for yield-driven optimization, the reliance on heuristic algorithms over more robust AI decision-making occasionally led to purity issues and inefficient reaction pathfinding. Another recent example is the Mobile Laboratory Robots (MOLAR) platform, developed at Center for Life Science Automation (CELISCA), which uses Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) to transport labware and materials across multi-floor laboratory environments [154]. MOLAR robots can autonomously interact with elevators, doors, and workstations, while the Sample and Module Manager (SAMI) software system (by Beckman Coulter Life Sciences) orchestrates workflows across distributed laboratory equipment. Compared to manual handling, MOLAR improves throughput, reduces contamination risks, and enables reproducible, 24/7 operation. This illustrates how mobile robotics can go beyond single-task chemists to form robust infrastructures that address reproducibility and standardization challenges. Recently, a compact autonomous platform [139] has emerged that prioritizes portability, modularity, and real-time control. The system developed in Cronin's lab is a suitcase-size portable chemical instrument yet can perform complex synthetic sequences. Using the universal chemical programming language γDL [155], literature protocols are compiled into executable code and automatically rendered as bespoke "module-monolith" reactionware cartridges; a programmable gas/vacuum manifold and syringe-pump fluidic backbone execute unit operations, while a pressure-fingerprint sensor enables remote quality control of every step. The platform synthesized five small organic molecules, four oligopeptides, and four oligonucleotides in good yields and purities. This achievement illustrates how code-driven cartridges plus compact hardware can democratize on-demand, reproducible synthesis beyond well-equipped labs.

Looking forward, compact and mobile systems are expected to play a key role in field-deployable synthesis, resource-limited environments, and distributed manufacturing scenarios. By combining AI-enabled decision-making with scalable hardware, such platforms can serve as low-cost extensions or nodes within larger, cloud-connected experimental ecosystems. However, challenges remain in achieving robustness, interoperability, and standardization across platforms. As recent advances in edge computing, battery technology, and miniaturized sensing mature, these systems are likely to become increasingly autonomous, intelligent, and impactful across a broad spectrum of scientific disciplines. Mobile robotics and compact systems should be viewed not merely as scaled-down versions of large self-driving laboratories, but as complementary technologies that democratize access, strengthen

reproducibility, and expand the reach of autonomous experimentation to a broader spectrum of audiences and applications. However, a broader deployment raises ethical and governance considerations, such as data integrity, safe handling of hazardous reagents, and dual-use risks, which are discussed in previous chapter.

3.6. Software for self-driving laboratories

Building an AI lab requires versatile software frameworks. ChemOS 2.0 [156] is one such adaptable platform inspired by UNIX architecture, offering small, specialized functions combined for device communication, data management, and simulations via integrated DFT calculations. ChemOS 2.0 supports modular integration with robotic systems, enabling seamless control over diverse experimental protocols. Its built-in ML modules can optimize reaction conditions autonomously, further enhancing the lab's self-driving capabilities. The "LabArchiver" module automatically logs experimental metadata, addressing reproducibility challenges in high-throughput workflows. Its web interface ensures user-friendly operation, with advantages including scalability, flexibility, reproducibility, and error handling. ChemCrow [157] based on GPT-4 integrate 18 specialized tools divided into four categories: general tools, molecular tools, safety tools, and reaction tools. It uses a multi-agent system where specialized tools work collaboratively with the GPT-4 Planner module to tackle complex chemical synthesis tasks, including reaction optimization and safety validation. Safety tools include a toxicity predictor trained on EPA datasets, reducing hazardous intermediate generation. This toxicity predictor specifically flagged high-risk intermediates in synthetic routes involving halogenated solvents, improving environmental safety. ChemCrow validates results and bridges gaps between hardware and software in chemical labs. However, its reliance on GPT-4 introduces potential bias stemming from the pre-trained model's limitations, requiring external validation for critical synthesis predictions. Complementary to the orchestration frameworks, the universal chemical programming language χ DL has emerged as a platform-agnostic standard for encoding and executing chemical protocols [155]. χ DL translates experimental procedures into machine-readable instructions that can be executed across diverse robotic hardware, from Chemputer systems to Opentrons pipetting robots and multi-axis collaborative robots (cobots), without reformatting. By abstracting chemistry into a concise set of unit operations (typically ~50 lines of code per reaction), χ DL ensures reproducibility, minimizes tacit knowledge loss, and allows the same synthesis to be performed reliably in different laboratories worldwide. Importantly, χ DL enables collaborative "ChemTorrent"-style workflows, where protocols can be distributed, validated, and optimized across multiple peers, enhancing transparency and accelerating the sharing of synthetic knowledge.

Taken together ChemOS, ChemCrow, and χ DL illustrate complementary layers of digital infrastructure for self-driving laboratories: orchestration (ChemOS), AI planning and reasoning (ChemCrow), and standardized protocol encoding (χ DL). Their integration is essential for achieving reproducibility, democratization, and scalability in autonomous chemical research.

3.7. Community efforts toward standardized and FAIR data

An important challenge for AI-driven materials discovery lies in the availability of high-quality datasets that are fully aligned with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles [158,159]. To this end, the community has invested considerable effort into developing shared schemas, ontologies, and programmatic interfaces that make materials data more AI-ready. A major step forward has been the introduction of the OPTIMADE API, which enables federated access to heterogeneous materials repositories and thereby reduces fragmentation [159–162]. Alongside this, large-scale initiatives such as the Materials Project, NOMAD, and Materials Cloud provide curated datasets and metadata frameworks, while domain-specific efforts like the

Open Catalyst Project (OC20/OC22) have established benchmarks, leaderboards, and standardized data splits for surface and catalysis problems. Together, these resources are beginning to define common ground for reproducibility and comparison across laboratories. Complementing these efforts, the MaRDA FAIR Materials Microscopy and LIMS Working Groups have issued community recommendations that (i) specify comprehensive, instrument- and context-rich microscopy metadata using standardized vocabularies and persistent identifiers, and (ii) provide pragmatic guidance for selecting and deploying LIMS, including cost/benefit analyses, stakeholder roles, and schema best practices-converging on actionable paths to FAIR-by-design laboratory workflows [163].

Despite these advances, significant gaps remain. Many repositories still rely on bespoke formats, synthesis procedures are rarely shared in machine-readable form, and negative or failed experiments (also crucial for training robust and unbiased AI models) are often omitted. Recent initiatives, such as AI4Mater, explicitly call for unified benchmarking protocols, inclusion of negative data, and community-driven curation of metadata-rich experimental datasets. In parallel, efforts to encode laboratory protocols in standardized languages (e.g., χ DL) promise to enhance reproducibility by linking procedures, datasets, and models within a common digital framework. MaRDA's microscopy and LIMS guidance directly targets these gaps by advocating minimal-yet-sufficient metadata sets, domain-relevant ontologies (e.g., HMSA, NeXus/NXem), open formats (e.g., TIFF/HDF5), and interoperable PID-centric data models that tie samples, instruments, datasets, and workflows across repositories, thereby operationalizing FAIR and accelerating AI-ready data creation at scale [163]. By aligning technical infrastructure with FAIR standards and fostering collective stewardship of open datasets, the community is laying the foundation for more interoperable, reproducible, and ultimately more impactful AI-assisted materiomics.

4. LLMs and agents in materials discovery

The rapid progress of LLMs has opened a new frontier in scientific discovery, extending beyond narrow surrogate models toward systems capable of reasoning, dialogue, and hypothesis generation. In contrast to conventional ML models, often designed for a single property or task, LLMs offer a flexible interface between researchers and computational infrastructure. Their conversational nature reduces the technical barriers traditionally associated with advanced modeling, enabling non-experts to query data, design simulations, and generate hypotheses in natural language. This democratization of access holds particular promise in materials science, a field where data are fragmented across scales and disciplines and where the cost of training and deploying bespoke models has limited broader participation.

A clear example of this potential was provided by Luu et al., who developed BioinspiredLLM [164]. Biomaterials exhibit hierarchical structures and exceptional functional properties, yet research in this domain has remained fragmented, with tools such as AlphaFold unable to generate cross-domain synthesis strategies or novel hypotheses. By fine-tuning Llama-2/Orca-2 on more than 1000 peer-reviewed articles using Q–A distillation, the authors created a model that substantially outperformed its base versions in knowledge retrieval, hypothesis generation, and assistive tasks. Although issues such as hallucination and misinformation persist, necessitating human oversight, the study demonstrated the power of domain-specific fine-tuning to unlock capabilities well beyond those of general-purpose LLMs. Beyond retrieval and ideation, recent experimental-AI studies demonstrate full "AI-to-bench" loops in which LLMs propose hypotheses and procedures that are then validated in the laboratory. Luu et al. [165] combine a fine-tuned domain model (BioinspiredLLM) with retrieval-augmented generation, agentic refinement, and a hierarchical sampling strategy to generate design concepts and executable protocols; they then validate outputs by fabricating humidity-responsive constructs and a novel pollen-based

adhesive with measured shear strength. This work illustrates how LLM-assisted ideation can be translated into tractable experiments, complementing brute-force exploration (e.g., GNOME-style pipelines) when domain priors and structured inference are leveraged.

More broadly, the question of how to best adapt LLMs for scientific use remains under active investigation. Lu et al. [166] systematically evaluated four strategies: (i) continued pretraining, where the model is exposed to domain-specific data; (ii) supervised fine-tuning, using Q–A or instruction datasets; (iii) preference optimization, aligning outputs with human or task-specific criteria; and (iv) model merging, where multiple fine-tuned models are combined into a new one. Their findings revealed that scale matters—emergent behaviors were observed only in larger models, not in smaller ones. That data quality is critical, with clean, curated datasets yielding better outcomes than noisy, extended ones. Yet another problem lies in the fragmentation of knowledge about material properties across scales and disciplines. To address the fragmentation of knowledge across atomistic, continuum, and engineering scales, Ghafarollahi et al. introduced MechGPT [167], a domain-specialized LLM fine-tuned for mechanics and materials science. Unlike general models, MechGPT enables cross-domain connections, linking concepts from atomistic modeling, continuum mechanics, and even interdisciplinary analogies, thereby generating more coherent and insightful outputs for hypothesis generation and scientific discovery.

A persistent challenge in materials discovery is the automation of hypothesis generation and refinement at a scale that surpasses the capacity of any single LLM. To address this, Ghafarollahi and Buehler introduced a series of multi-agent frameworks that emulate the collaborative and critical nature of scientific research. Their first system, SciAgents [168], combined ontological knowledge graphs, LLM reasoning, and specialized agent roles to generate and iteratively refine hypotheses, testing both pre-programmed and fully autonomous interaction modes. While this advanced hypothesis generation, another gap persisted in protein discovery, as tools such as AlphaFold excel at folding prediction but do not cover the entire discovery loop. To bridge this, the same group developed ProtAgents [169], which equipped LLMs with access to specialized tools for protein design, folding prediction, physics-based simulations, and literature retrieval, representing the first step toward a closed multi-agent system for protein science. Building further, they introduced Sparks [170], which explicitly targeted the full discovery cycle from hypothesis generation to final reporting. Sparks employed a generation–reflection design, where every agent in its four modules (idea generation, testing, refinement, documentation) was paired with a critic, ensuring that hypotheses were pushed beyond the models' training data and refined through iterative cycles, effectively closing the gap in autonomous protein discovery. Most recently, Ghafarollahi and Buehler presented AtomAgents [171], extending the multi-agent paradigm to alloy design. This system integrates LLMs, physics-based atomistic simulations, multimodal analysis, and multi-agent reasoning into a single workflow. Unlike earlier task-specific AI tools, AtomAgents functions as a dynamic autonomous scientist, capable not only of retrieving knowledge but also of simulating, analyzing, and validating hypotheses, thereby bridging the gap between static surrogate models and a truly autonomous discovery engine.

In parallel with advances in LLMs and agent-based frameworks, natural language processing (NLP) has emerged as an equally important enabler of materials discovery [172]. NLP techniques have been used to mine vast corpora of scientific publications, patents, and technical reports, extracting structured knowledge such as synthesis protocols, materials properties, and structure–function relationships. Domain-specific models like ChemDataExtractor [173], MatSciBERT [174], and SteelBERT [175] have shown how automated text mining can transform unstructured literature into machine-readable datasets that feed into databases and inform downstream machine-learning tasks. By converting natural language into structured knowledge, these models reduce the burden of manual data curation and allow researchers to

build more comprehensive and diverse training sets for computational discovery. Recent trends point toward an even tighter integration of NLP with LLM-based systems. Instead of simply extracting entities or relations, modern approaches aim to couple text mining with reasoning and hypothesis generation, enabling natural language itself to serve as both an input and an output modality for discovery. Retrieval-augmented NLP pipelines, for example, are being used to ground LLMs in curated scientific corpora, thereby mitigating hallucination and ensuring factual accuracy. Moreover, conversational natural language interfaces are increasingly recognized as a democratizing layer, allowing non-specialists to query heterogeneous datasets and simulation results directly, without requiring deep expertise in coding or database structures. In this way, NLP serves not only as the foundation for domain-specific LLMs but also as a critical guardrail for their responsible and effective deployment in materials science.

Taken together, these developments illustrate how LLMs and agent-based systems are beginning to transform the scientific workflow. By providing intuitive conversational interfaces, they lower the barriers for researchers without deep coding expertise and broaden participation in advanced computational discovery. At the same time, their adoption introduces new risks that must be explicitly managed. LLMs inherit biases from their training data, which may distort research priorities if not critically examined, and they remain prone to hallucination or overconfident responses that could mislead users when unverified. Multi-agent systems, while powerful, also raise concerns about error propagation in iterative hypothesis generation, as well as issues of reproducibility, data provenance, and responsible use. Recent trends highlight growing recognition of these challenges, with the community moving toward embedding guardrails such as retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) [176,177] for grounding outputs in curated knowledge bases, uncertainty quantification to flag low-confidence predictions, and human-on-the-loop oversight models that maintain expert control of decision-critical steps. Particular emphasis should be placed on transparent reporting standards, open benchmarking frameworks, and ethical governance consistent with FAIR data principles and responsible AI practices [178–180]. If developed within such frameworks, LLMs and agentic systems could indeed democratize access to powerful computational tools and accelerate hypothesis-driven exploration. Their long-term impact, however, will depend not only on technical advances but also on the establishment of robust safeguards that ensure reliability, equity, and trust in AI-driven scientific discovery.

5. Perspectives and outlook

AI has firmly established itself as a transformative force across the complete materials science pipeline ranging from property prediction and generative design to synthesis automation and in situ characterization. The past decade has witnessed a rapid evolution of methods, frameworks, and platforms that push the boundaries of what is experimentally and computationally possible. However, despite these successes, the field remains in a dynamic and transitional phase, with numerous opportunities and critical challenges yet to be fully addressed. A central limitation lies in the fragmentation of current AI approaches. Most ML models are task-specific, designed for narrowly defined objectives such as band gap prediction, reaction yield optimization, or atomic force field fitting. While such specialization can yield impressive accuracy, it often comes at the cost of generalizability and interoperability. Developing unified or modular frameworks perhaps utilizing foundation models trained on multi-domain, multimodal data represents an urgent need. Such systems could flexibly adapt to diverse materials classes and tasks without retraining from scratch.

Equally important is the issue of data infrastructure. Although significant progress has been made through large initiatives mentioned above, the lack of standardized, high-quality experimental datasets, particularly for synthesis conditions and failed experiments (i.e., containing also negative data), remains a major bottleneck. Addressing this

will require community-driven efforts toward open-access, FAIR-compliant repositories that include not only successful outcomes but also negative results and metadata-rich characterization data. Additionally, the development of domain-specific ontologies and interoperable formats for AI-ready datasets will be critical to enable meaningful comparisons across different platforms and materials systems.

Another emerging concern is the computational sustainability of modern AI methods. Large generative models and diffusion-based frameworks offer impressive predictive and creative capabilities but are associated with substantial energy demands during training and inference. Recent syntheses of AI energy footprints report that training state-of-the-art foundation models can require on the order of 10^3 MWh of electricity (e.g., above 1287 MWh for GPT-3), i.e., comparable to the annual electricity use of several hundred average households, underscoring the need for energy-efficient architectures and carbon-aware scheduling [181]. In the context of materiomics, these concerns are particularly pressing, as scaling high-throughput AI pipelines without accounting for energy demand could offset the societal benefits of accelerated discovery. Future research must prioritize the development of energy-efficient algorithms, compressed model architectures, and on-device inference strategies, especially as these tools are scaled toward deployment in resource-constrained environments. From a methodological standpoint, one of the most promising but underdeveloped directions is the tight integration of AI with physical and chemical knowledge. Many ML models still operate as “black boxes”, which hampers trust and interpretability. Physically informed ML, hybrid physics-AI frameworks, and explainable AI are therefore critical frontiers. These approaches can embed domain knowledge into models, enforce known constraints, and provide insights into underlying mechanisms thereby bridging the gap between statistical accuracy and scientific understanding.

In parallel, surrogate modeling for scale transitions has emerged as a complementary strategy to accelerate expensive simulations and couple models across length and time scales. Recent works in mechanics demonstrate how ML surrogates can bridge atomistic and continuum regimes, efficiently transferring knowledge across modeling hierarchies [182–184]. These efforts exemplify how AI can be leveraged to build multiscale ecosystems. Such approaches underscore the potential for cross-fertilization between, e.g., mechanics and materiomics, highlighting AI's role in unifying methodologies across traditionally separate disciplines.

A major opportunity lies in the autonomous laboratory revolution, where AI not only predicts or plans, but also executes and adapts. While robotic platforms have demonstrated closed-loop synthesis and characterization in specific domains, a comprehensive, end-to-end self-driving laboratory remains rare. Expanding the functionality of autonomous labs to encompass a broader array of material types, synthesis techniques, and multimodal characterization, while ensuring reliability, scalability, and safety, is a challenge ripe for innovation. Particularly underexplored is the integration of real-time AI-driven decision-making in high-throughput and in situ characterization workflows, which could enable the discovery of dynamic materials and metastable states otherwise inaccessible via static methods.

Hand-in-hand with the technology progress the robust ethical framework has to be developed to minimize potential misuse. As AI systems become more influential in research decisions, ethical considerations must be integrated directly into their development and deployment. Algorithmic biases stemming from unbalanced datasets (e.g., favoring positive over negative results) may skew discovery pipelines, while black-box predictions risk eroding scientific trust if not accompanied by transparency and interpretability. Moreover, disparities in access to computational and technological resources could reinforce inequities between well-funded institutions and smaller laboratories, counteracting the democratizing promise of AI. Finally, the dual-use potential of AI-generated synthesis pathways underscores the need for robust oversight frameworks that balance innovation with

safety and societal responsibility.

At the level of technology translation, a significant challenge remains in bridging the gap between AI-generated predictions and real-world implementation. The synthesizability, stability, and scalability of predicted materials are often not evaluated in generative models. Synthesis-aware design, combined with multi-objective optimization (e.g., combining performance, cost, toxicity, and processability), must become standard practice. Moreover, AI frameworks must be coupled with techno-economic analysis and life cycle assessment tools to guide responsible and impactful material innovation. Finally, the human dimension cannot be neglected. The successful integration of AI into materials research depends on more than algorithms and data, because it requires cultural, educational, and organizational change. Future chemists and materials scientists must be trained in both domain expertise and data science, while interdisciplinary collaboration between AI researchers, experimentalists, theorists, and engineers must be structurally supported. Again, ethical frameworks must guide the deployment of AI in materials R&D, addressing issues such as data privacy, intellectual property, algorithmic bias, and environmental impact. Taken together, these considerations point to fundamental challenges for the next generation of machine learning in materials science (Fig. 7).

The future of AI-assisted materials science will hinge on progress mostly in five key areas: i) model generalization and modularity toward development of adaptable, reusable AI frameworks applicable across materials classes; ii) data quality and availability to continue in building comprehensive, structured, and open datasets covering both positive and negative results; iii) energy-efficient computation to design AI systems that maximize performance while minimizing computational and environmental cost; iv) human-AI collaboration and explainability via ensuring interpretability, physical insight, and trust through hybrid and explainable models; v) real-world validation and deployment bridging the gap between predictions and applications through synthesis-aware design, automation, and techno-economic analysis. By addressing these challenges in tandem, the field can move beyond narrow demonstrations toward a truly integrated, scalable, and sustainable AI-powered materials innovation ecosystem one that combines machine intelligence with human creativity to unlock the next generation of advanced materials.

6. Conclusion

AI is fundamentally reshaping materials science by delivering unprecedented efficiency and predictive accuracy. Nevertheless, significant challenges remain. Current ML models often lack sufficient transferability, resulting in many specialized models rather than a single general-purpose model. Additionally, a noticeable gap persists between computational predictions and experimentally measured properties, primarily due to insufficient integration of characterization techniques. Additionally, current AI models often involve significant power consumption, posing sustainability concerns. Future research should aim to develop hybrid AI methodologies that seamlessly combine design, synthesis, and characterization, particularly within autonomous laboratory frameworks. Reducing energy requirements and enhancing computational efficiency of AI models will also be an essential focus. The establishment of comprehensive, high-quality, and ideally open-source databases will be crucial for training robust, generalizable AI models. Addressing these challenges will allow AI to fully realize its transformative potential in materials science. However, even in this advanced scenario, scientists will continue to play a pivotal role, translating AI-generated data and hypotheses into practical solutions for real-world problems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Martin Otyepka: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Martin Pykal:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft,

Fig. 7. Summary of major community challenges in machine learning for materials science and representative methodological approaches to address them.

Visualization, Conceptualization. **Michal Otyepka**: Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Mi.O. has share in InSiliBio (France) focused on membrane biosimulations and ATOMIVER, s.r.o. (Czechia) focused on development of supercapacitor electrode materials. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The authors used Artificial Intelligence language models to improve the clarity and fluency of the manuscript. The authors carefully edited the content afterwards.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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